

Optimal outcome in early-onset regressive autism: functional remission documented in a context of limited diagnostic access following a naturopathic intervention

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Abstract

Introduction: Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterised by high aetiological and clinical heterogeneity. In recent years, the need to investigate integrative approaches that account for its possible multisystemic nature has been increasingly recognised. From a complex systems perspective, effective interventions should be necessarily multidimensional and adaptive.

Case presentation: A 3-year-old male participant of Chilean nationality was evaluated following a progressive sociocommunicative regression with complete loss of expressive language and onset of stereotypies. In the absence of standardised diagnostic tools, a neurologist established an informal clinical diagnosis of "autistic regression", documenting severe impairment across multiple neurodevelopmental domains (baseline ATEC: 83).

Intervention: An individualised Naturopathic Complex Intervention (NCI) was applied over 24 months (July 2020 – July 2022), structured around three components: (1) trophology and dietary exclusion based on documented IgG hypersensitivities; (2) personalised naturopathic supplementation with analytical monitoring; and (3) parental coaching with structured home-based neurocognitive stimulation.

Results: An 84.3% reduction in symptom severity was observed (ATEC: 83 → 13) over the 24 months of active intervention. External reassessment using the ADOS-2, conducted under blinded diagnostic conditions at month 17 of the NCI, ruled out ASD (total score: 6; classification: Non-ASD; symptom level: LOW). Long-term neurological follow-up via QEEG at age 8 documented a mild attentional-executive profile, consistent with high-functioning residual neurodivergence.

Conclusions: The NCI was associated with a clinical trajectory consistent with functional remission (optimal outcome). The case illustrates, from a Latin American context with limited diagnostic access, that the absence of standardised baseline assessment tools does not preclude rigorous documentation of clinical evolution when validated follow-up metrics (ATEC), blinded external reassessments (ADOS-2) and objective neurological monitoring (QEEG) are appropriately combined. Additionally, the case documents how a prior diagnostic label can act as an interpretive lens modulating the conclusions of subsequent assessments, a phenomenon described in the literature as diagnostic overshadowing.

Keywords: autism spectrum disorder, optimal outcome, functional remission, diagnostic overshadowing, naturopathic intervention, case study, Latin American context

Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition of heterogeneous aetiology. [1-3] International guidelines acknowledge the need to investigate multimodal interventions that address its potential multisystemic involvement. [4-6] In this context, an individualised Naturopathic Complex Intervention (NCI), protocolised under the designation Katia Dolle Method© (KDM), was applied. This NCI addresses biological

imbalances interrelated with behavioural difficulties through immunonutrition, supplementation and structured parental coaching strategies aimed at modulating immunological, neuroendocrine and behavioural axes. This report documents the longitudinal evolution of a 3-year-old male child of Chilean nationality who received this NCI in a context of limited diagnostic access, evaluating the impact of biological factor modulation on the severity of his initial clinical presentation.

Case presentation

Following an apparently normotypical early development, the participant experienced a progressive sociocommunicative regression from the age of 2, with complete loss of previously acquired expressive language, failure to recognise close family members, regression in toilet training, onset of motor stereotypies and severe behavioural disturbances. At age 3 (July 2020), a neurologist established an informal clinical diagnosis of "autistic regression" without application of a standardised diagnostic battery — a common practice in the Chilean public health system given the limited availability of specialist resources. In the absence of a response to available conventional approaches and given the severity of the presentation, the family initiated the NCI exclusively. The main anamnestic data and baseline clinical and biological findings are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Initial diagnostic assessment

Assessment	Result	Interpretation
Clinical neurological evaluation	Informal clinical diagnosis: "autistic regression"	Assessment performed without standardised battery; context of limited diagnostic access (Chile, 2020)
ATEC (baseline)	Total score: 83 — Language: 22 / Sociability: 18 / Sensory-Cognitive: 21 / Health-Behaviour: 22	Moderate-to-severe range
Clinical observations reported by caregivers	Progressive sociocommunicative regression from age 2: complete loss of expressive language, failure to recognise family members, regression in toilet training, onset of motor stereotypies, insomnia, sensory hypersensitivity, absence of functional play, disruptive behaviours	Regressive phenotype with severe impairment across multiple neurodevelopmental domains

Note. ATEC: Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist.

Table 2

Baseline clinical and biological findings

Category	Findings
Behavioural characteristics reported by parents	Sociocommunicative regression with complete loss of expressive language; absent response to name; reduced eye contact; disruptive

Category	Findings
	behaviours; motor stereotypies (toe-walking, repetitive pacing); object fixations; severe food selectivity; nocturnal awakenings; sensory hypersensitivity; absent functional and symbolic play; limited awareness of danger
Relevant developmental history	Gestational exposure to chronic stress factors; extracurricular vaccination administered weeks before onset of the regressive episode; separation from primary attachment figure during a critical period of neurodevelopment (first and second year of life)
Urinary analysis — toxic metals (post-EDTA provocation)	Elevated metals: As (170 µg/g Cr, ref. <30), Cs (30, ref. <11), Cd (0.57, ref. <0.16), Pb (2.5, ref. <1.1), Hg (1.4, ref. <0.7), Ni (18, ref. <7)
Faecal microbiology	Intestinal dysbiosis with dysbiotic flora (<i>Brevundimonas diminuta</i> , <i>Citrobacter freundii</i> complex, <i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> , <i>Pseudomonas putida</i> group); imbalanced beneficial flora (reduced <i>Lactobacillus</i> spp.); no yeast isolated
Food hypersensitivity (IgG, type III reaction)	51 out of 180 allergens positive (ImuPro Basic+). Highly elevated (≥18 µg/ml): oats (93.5), almond (81.3), quinoa (55.8), coconut (60.2), hazelnut (53.7), pistachio (46.3), flaxseed (46.4), pumpkin seeds (42.0), hen's egg (37.4), cashew (26.1), among others

Note. As: arsenic; Cs: caesium; Cd: cadmium; Pb: lead; Hg: mercury; Ni: nickel. Urinary, faecal microbiology and food hypersensitivity analyses were performed at independent external laboratories at month 13 of the NCI (August–September 2021).

Intervention

An individualised multimodal NCI (KDM) was applied over 24 months of active intervention (July 2020 – July 2022). Functional changes correspond to 24 net months of effective NCI, structured around three main components:

- 1) **trophology:** substitution of foods triggering delayed hypersensitivity (IgG), analytically documented at month 13, to reduce the inflammatory cytokine cascade and correct dysbiosis.
- 2) **naturopathic supplementation:** rotational and sequential protocol, organised in bimonthly blocks and reassessed through analytical monitoring, aimed at immunological, neurological and neuroendocrine modulation, as well as detoxification processes.
- 3) **parental coaching:** health education, behavioural management and structured home-based neurocognitive stimulation (language, motor skills and social abilities).

Therapeutic follow-up was conducted continuously via telemedicine. No adverse effects were recorded throughout the intervention, with the exception of a transient exacerbation during the first two months of supplementation that resolved spontaneously.

Follow-up and results

The psychometric assessments, laboratory analyses and parental reports conducted periodically throughout the longitudinal follow-up document the developmental trajectory and functional changes of the participant (Tables 3 and 4, Figure 1).

Table 3

Longitudinal evolution of psychometric and biological parameters

Date	Assessment	Results
July 2020 (age 3); baseline	ATEC	Total score: 83 (moderate-to-severe range). Language: 22; Sociability: 18; Sensory-Cognitive: 21; Health-Behaviour: 22
~January 2021 (age 3y 7m); month 6 of NCI	ATEC	Total score: 24 (mild range). Language: 2; Sociability: 4; Sensory-Cognitive: 1; Health-Behaviour: 17
August–September 2021 (age 4); month 13 of NCI	Laboratory analyses (urine, faeces, IgG food hypersensitivity)	Elevated toxic metals, intestinal dysbiosis with dysbiotic flora, multiple food hypersensitivities (see Table 2)
July 2022 (age 5); month 24 of NCI	ATEC	Total score: 13 (subclinical range). Language: 1; Sociability: 3; Sensory-Cognitive: 2; Health-Behaviour: 7

Note. ATEC: Autism Treatment Evaluation Checklist. Laboratory analyses were conducted at month 13 of the NCI, once initial clinical evolution had been established.

Table 4

Longitudinal evolution of qualitative clinical milestones reported by caregivers

Date	Observations reported by caregivers
July 2020 (baseline)	Severe symptomatology: complete absence of expressive language, frequent disruptive behaviours, motor stereotypies, marked sensory hypersensitivity, extreme food selectivity, nocturnal awakenings, absence of functional and social play
~January 2021 (month 6)	Re-emergence of functional verbal language with short sentences; re-establishment of joint attention and eye contact; marked reduction in tantrums; emergence of functional and early symbolic play (imitates sweeping, plays with puppets); proactive peer interaction; normalisation of gastrointestinal pattern; remission of recurrent infectious episodes
November 2021 (month ~17)	Blinded external ADOS-2 assessment: no symptomatology compatible with autism spectrum disorder. Functional language in sentences of 3+ words with appropriate grammatical markers; spontaneous initiation of joint attention; reciprocal social interaction present; absence of repetitive behaviours during assessment
July 2022 (month 24 — end of active NCI)	Consolidated functional remission: spontaneous and fluid socialisation; broad vocabulary; complex symbolic play; acquisition of more than 10 social games; mainstream school integration without support or curriculum adaptation; teachers report no difference from neurotypical peers; independence in daily living activities. Mild residual neurodivergence: occasional difficulty with double meanings and humour, sporadic morning tantrums, mild residual abdominal bloating

Note. Clinical milestones were reported by caregivers during therapeutic follow-up based on non-standardised observational records and reflect functional changes perceived in everyday settings.

Psychometric metrics

Longitudinal psychometric assessment documented a progressive and sustained reduction in symptom severity as measured by the ATEC (Figure 1). Severity declined from a baseline score of 83 (moderate-to-severe range) to 24 at month 6 of intervention, reaching 13 at the end of the 24 months of active NCI (subclinical range). This 84.3% reduction represents a clinically significant transition across all assessed domains, most pronounced in language (22 → 1), sociability (18 → 3) and sensory-cognitive awareness (21 → 2).

Figure 1

Evolution of ATEC scores throughout follow-up

Note. The figure illustrates a progressive reduction in symptom severity from the moderate-to-severe range (83 points) to the subclinical range (13 points) over 24 months of active NCI, representing an 84.3% reduction. The dashed line represents the 30-point threshold commonly associated with low symptom severity. The vertical dotted line marks the timing of the blinded external ADOS-2 reassessment (month 17), which concluded Non-ASD.

External reassessments and long-term neurological follow-up

Two independent external assessments were conducted at different time points throughout the follow-up (Table 5).

Assessment A was conducted in November 2021 (month 17 of NCI) by an ADOS-2-accredited speech and language therapist at an independent external specialist centre, under conditions of diagnostic blinding with respect to the prior diagnosis of autistic regression. The participant was then aged 4 years and 5 months. Application of the ADOS-2 Module 2 yielded a global total score of 6 (Social Affect: 4; Restricted and Repetitive Behaviours: 2), with an ADOS-2 Comparison Score of 3 (LOW level). The classification concluded: Non-ASD. The report described functional language with the use of three or more word sentences, spontaneous initiation of joint attention, reciprocal social interaction and absence of repetitive or stereotyped behaviours during the assessment.

Assessment B was conducted in April 2026, when the participant was aged 8, and consisted of a quantitative electroencephalography (QEEG) study aimed at exploring neurophysiological correlates of mild difficulties in concentration and comprehension in a child enrolled in mainstream schooling without any support needs. This assessment was

conducted with full knowledge of the prior diagnosis of ASD level 1, provided by the family as clinical context. The study showed excellent test-retest reliability (0.95) and revealed a pattern of amplitude deficits in the delta, theta and beta bands with frontal predominance (Fz), persistent prefrontal hypo-coherence in both conditions (eyes closed and open), and hypercoherence in the right temporal region across all analysed bands. The alpha activity peak (9.5 Hz at Pz) was within age-normative ranges.

These neurophysiological findings, considered independently of the diagnostic label provided in the referral, are consistent with a profile of mild frontal attentional-executive dysfunction. This pattern — frontal theta-beta deficit with prefrontal hypo-coherence — is classically described in the literature for profiles of inattention and executive dysfunction [9,10] and does not constitute an ASD-specific marker. In the absence of the prior diagnosis, the same data would have oriented the clinical interpretation towards a mild inattention profile or high-functioning residual neurodivergence, in line with what has been described in optimal outcome cases [7]. This contrast between Assessment A (blinded, Non-ASD) and Assessment B (non-blinded, interpreted within the prior ASD framework) documents a phenomenon of interpretive contamination by diagnostic label: prior clinical information oriented the conclusions of an assessment whose objective data, analysed under blinding, would have led to a different reading. This constitutes a specific form of diagnostic overshadowing [8] with direct implications for the design of reassessment protocols in cases of possible optimal outcome.

Table 5

Comparison of external reassessments

Assessment	Methodology	Instruments	Key results	Diagnostic conclusion
Assessment A — Independent external specialist centre (November 2021, month ~17 of NCI)	No knowledge of prior diagnosis of autistic regression (blinded)	ADOS-2 Module 2 (accredited examiner)	Global total score: 6 (SA: 4; RRB: 2); ADOS-2 Comparison Score: 3 (LOW); functional communication with 3+ word sentences; no repetitive behaviours; reciprocal social interaction present	Non-ASD. Level of autism-associated symptoms: LOW
Assessment B — Neurofeedback centre (April 2026, long-term follow-up at age 8)	With knowledge of prior diagnosis of ASD level 1 (non-blinded)	QEEG (quantitative electroencephalography, 10/20 system, Neuroguide normative database; test-retest reliability: 0.95)	Frontal (Fz) amplitude deficits in delta, theta and beta bands; persistent prefrontal hypo-coherence in both conditions; right temporal hypercoherence across all bands; generalised deficit in eyes-open condition; alpha peak 9.5 Hz at Pz (age-appropriate)	Neurophysiological profile interpreted within the framework of the prior ASD diagnosis. Analysed independently, the pattern is consistent with mild frontal attentional-executive dysfunction, non-specific for ASD [9,10]

Discussion

The results suggest that the NCI contributed to a clinical trajectory consistent with functional remission or optimal outcome [7]. After 24 months of active intervention, the participant achieved social, academic and behavioural functioning within normative ranges, with mainstream school integration without educational support, and minimal residual neurodivergence documented through objective neurological follow-up.

The present case adds a distinctive dimension to the series by representing the reality of a Latin American health system with limited diagnostic access. The absence of a standardised diagnostic battery at baseline — determined by context rather than by lack of clinical rigour — is the norm, not the exception, for most Latin American families of children with ASD. Documenting a case of this nature contributes to broadening the ecological validity of the series findings, demonstrating that evolution towards optimal outcome can be rigorously documented even in contexts with limited diagnostic resources, provided that validated follow-up metrics (ATEC), blinded external reassessments (ADOS-2) and objective neurophysiological assessment (QEEG) are appropriately combined.

In this context, the NCI targeted the modulation of disrupted biological systems — including intestinal dysbiosis, IgG-mediated food hypersensitivity and heavy metal burden — through immunonutrition, supplementation and parental training strategies, consistent with research associating gastrointestinal dysfunction and micronutrient deficiencies with ASD. [11-13] The 84.3% reduction in ATEC severity, together with the ADOS-2 reassessment ruling out ASD at month 17 of the intervention, suggests a clinically relevant impact of the NCI.

The long-term follow-up via QEEG at age 8 offers a perspective not previously documented in the series and captures one of the most relevant findings of this case: the social persistence of the ASD diagnostic label in a child who had clinically outgrown it. As the QEEG study was requested with a prior diagnosis of ASD level 1 as clinical context, the objective QEEG findings — consistent with a mild attentional-executive profile — were interpreted within that framework. The same data, analysed under blinding, would in all likelihood have led to a different conclusion. This phenomenon, whereby the diagnostic label acts as a lens that orients and constrains subsequent clinical interpretation, has been described in the literature as a form of diagnostic overshadowing [8] and has direct implications for clinical practice: it underlines the need for reassessments in cases of possible optimal outcome to be conducted under conditions of diagnostic blinding, particularly when using tools sensitive to prior clinical context.

This study presents the limitations inherent to its single-case design: absence of a control group, inability to establish causality, and partial reliance on parental report for qualitative milestones. Nonetheless, unlike other cases in the series where instrumental verification of remission was not available, the present case includes a blinded external ADOS-2 reassessment that ruled out ASD during the intervention, strengthening the clinical validity of the findings. Furthermore, the results are consistent with those documented in prior cases in the MKD-TEA series, in which application of the same individualised NCI was associated with trajectories compatible with functional remission across different profiles — different ages of onset, different nationalities and different baseline severity levels. The convergence of these findings, while not supporting robust causal inference, justifies the development of prospective studies with larger samples and controlled designs.

Conclusions

Application of an NCI in a 3-year-old child with a regressive phenotype, diagnosed in a context of limited diagnostic access, was associated with a rapid clinical trajectory consistent with functional remission (optimal outcome). After 24 months of active biological intervention, the participant achieved remission of core sociocommunicative deficits, mainstream school integration without support and an 84.3% reduction in ATEC severity, with minimal residual neurodivergence documented through long-term neurological follow-up.

The case illustrates that the absence of standardised diagnostic tools at baseline, common in Latin American contexts, does not preclude rigorous documentation of clinically relevant evolution when validated follow-up metrics, blinded external reassessments and objective neurophysiological assessment are appropriately combined.

Furthermore, the contrast between the blinded ADOS-2 reassessment (Non-ASD, month 17 of NCI) and the subsequent QEEG conducted with knowledge of the prior diagnosis documents how a diagnostic label can act as an interpretive lens modulating the clinical conclusions of objective assessments, constituting a specific form of diagnostic overshadowing with direct implications for the design of reassessment protocols in optimal outcome cases.

Family perspective

The participant's mother described the evolution observed in the following terms:

"In the schools he has attended he has done very well; the teachers are surprised and cannot believe he had severe autism — they find him a very intelligent, affectionate and sociable child. Academically he works at the same level as the other children and understands what he is asked to do. The truth is that Gael passes as just another child; neither adults nor the other children notice any difference, up to now."

"Gael entertains himself in many ways now; he plays football with his peers, plays with puppets and figures making them interact with each other [...] He loves cutting, writing letters, seeing books and naming what is in them [...] He is generally the one who initiates play and interaction with other children his age."

Informed consent

The authors certify that all consent forms have been obtained from the parents of the child. In these forms, the parents gave their consent for information related to the case to be published.

The parents of the child understand that their names and initials will not be published and that every effort will be made to conceal their identity, but that anonymity cannot be guaranteed.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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